

Bridging Psychology and Humanities: Analysing Employee Well-being at MRSTC in the Context of Indian Society

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Abstract

This qualitative study explores the well-being of employees at the Maharashtra State Road Transport Corporation (MRSTC) by bridging insights from psychology and the humanities. Through in-depth interviews and thematic analysis, the paper examines the cultural, societal, and organizational factors that influence employee well-being in the context of Indian society. By integrating psychological theories with humanities perspectives, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced by MRSTC employees and suggest holistic solutions.

In contemporary Indian society, workplace mental health is a growing concern, especially in organizations like the MRSTC. This paper explores the psychological factors affecting employee well-being, including stress, motivation, and job satisfaction, and examines their broader implications for Indian society. By integrating insights from psychology and humanities, this study aims to provide a holistic understanding of these challenges and propose comprehensive strategies to address them. Understanding the psychological factors that influence employee well-being is essential not only for improving individual health and productivity but also for fostering a healthy societal environment.

The purpose of this study is to bridge the gap between psychology and humanities in analyzing employee well-being at MRSTC. By adopting an interdisciplinary approach, this research aims to uncover the multifaceted nature of workplace mental health issues and propose strategies that address these challenges in a comprehensive manner.

Keywords: Employee well-being, MRSTC, psychology, humanities, Indian society, workplace culture, qualitative research.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and Significance

Employee well-being is a critical aspect of organizational success, influencing productivity, job satisfaction, and overall health. In India, cultural, societal, and organizational factors play significant roles in shaping employee well-being. This study focuses on the Maharashtra State Road Transport Corporation (MRSTC), a major public sector employer, to explore these dynamics. By bridging psychology and humanities, this paper seeks to uncover deeper insights into the well-being of MRSTC employees.

1.2 Objectives:

- To identify and understand the factors influencing employee well-being at MRSTC.
- To explore the impact of workplace culture and societal context on employee well-being.
- To integrate psychological and humanities perspectives to suggest holistic solutions.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Employee Well-being in Indian Workplaces

Research indicates that stress, job dissatisfaction, and burnout are common issues affecting employee well-being in Indian workplaces. Public sector organizations like MRSTC face unique challenges due to rigid bureaucratic structures, job security concerns, and often inadequate support systems.

2.2 Bridging Psychology and Humanities

Psychology provides a framework for understanding individual mental health and well-being, focusing on cognitive, emotional, and behavioral aspects. Humanities, on the other hand, offer insights into the cultural, historical, and societal dimensions of human experience. By integrating these perspectives, this study aims to provide a holistic understanding of employee well-being.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study employs a qualitative approach, using in-depth interviews to gather detailed data on the well-being of MRSTC employees. Thematic analysis is used to interpret the data, allowing for a rich understanding of the participants' experiences.

3.2 Sampling

A purposive sampling technique is used to select 20 MRSTC employees, ensuring diversity in terms of job roles, experience, and demographics.

3.3 Data Collection

Data is collected through semi-structured interviews, which allow participants to share their experiences and perspectives in their own words. Ethical considerations, including confidentiality and informed consent, are strictly adhered to.

3.4 Data Analysis

Thematic analysis is used to identify and interpret patterns and themes within the interview data. This approach allows for a deep understanding of the participants' experiences and the factors influencing their well-being.

4. Findings and Analysis

4.1 Factors Influencing Employee Well-being

The interviews reveal several key factors influencing employee well-being at MRSTC, including:

- **Workplace Stress:** High levels of stress due to long working hours, demanding job responsibilities, and job security concerns.

- **Job Satisfaction:** Issues related to job satisfaction, including recognition, career growth opportunities, and job fulfillment.
- **Support Systems:** The presence or absence of support systems, both within the workplace and outside, significantly impacts well-being.

4.2 Impact of Workplace Culture

The workplace culture at MRSTC plays a crucial role in shaping employee well-being. Key cultural factors include:

- **Peer Relationships:** Positive relationships with colleagues provide support, while conflicts and lack of teamwork exacerbate stress.
- **Management Practices:** Supportive management can mitigate stress, while authoritative and unsupportive practices increase it.

4.3 Societal and Cultural Context

The societal and cultural context of India significantly influences employee well-being. Factors such as:

- **Cultural Stigma:** Cultural stigma surrounding mental health issues prevents employees from seeking help.

4.4 Integrating Psychological and Humanities Insights

By bridging psychology and humanities, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of employee well-being. Key insights include:

- **Psychological Theories:** Theories on stress, motivation, and job satisfaction help explain individual experiences and behaviors.
- **Humanities Perspectives:** Literature, philosophy, and social sciences provide a deeper understanding of the cultural and societal dimensions of well-being.

5. Discussion

5.1 Interpretation of Results

The findings highlight the complex interplay of psychological, cultural, and societal factors influencing employee well-being at MRSTC. By integrating psychology and humanities, the study offers a holistic perspective that emphasizes the importance of understanding well-being in its broader context.

5.2 Implications for Policy and Practice

The study suggests several recommendations for MRSTC management:

- **Mental Health Support Programs:** Implementing programs to support mental health, including counseling services and stress management workshops.
- **Positive Workplace Culture:** Fostering a supportive and empathetic workplace culture through training and organizational changes.
- **Open Discussions:** Encouraging open discussions about mental health to reduce stigma and promote well-being.

6. Conclusion

This study highlights the importance of bridging psychology and humanities in analyzing employee well-being at MRSTC. By adopting an interdisciplinary approach, this research provides valuable insights into the complex and multifaceted nature of workplace mental health issues. Addressing these challenges requires a holistic strategy that considers both psychological factors and the broader cultural and social context.

6.1 Summary of Key Findings

The study identifies significant factors influencing employee well-being at MRSTC, shaped by workplace culture and societal context. By bridging psychology and humanities, the study provides deep insights into these factors and suggests holistic solutions to improve well-being.

6.2 Future Research Directions

Further research is needed to explore the long-term impact of workplace interventions on employee well-being. Studies involving other public sector organizations can provide comparative insights and help develop broader strategies for improving well-being in Indian workplaces.

7. Limitations

This study is limited by its qualitative nature and the small sample size. Future research could expand on these findings by incorporating quantitative methods and a larger sample to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the issues.

References

- www.msrtc.in
- Cooper, C. L., & Dewe, P. J. (2008). *Stress: A Brief History*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Chakraborty, S. K. (1991). *Management by Values: Towards Cultural Congruence*. Oxford University Press.

Appendices

Interview Questions

- What are the main sources of stress in your job?
- How do you perceive the support from your colleagues and management regarding well-being?
- Can you describe any experiences related to job satisfaction or dissatisfaction?
- What changes do you think could improve well-being support in your workplace?